

GENERAL OVERVIEW OF CULTURAL AND HUMANITARIAN RELATIONS BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND TURKEY

Sagatova Z.B.

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *The article analyses the cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey during the years of independence. It examines the historical background, current state, and prospects for cooperation in the fields of education, culture, art, tourism, and public diplomacy. Particular attention is paid to the role of cultural and humanitarian relations in strengthening bilateral relations between the two countries and their impact on the development of civil society in Uzbekistan and Turkey.*

Keywords: *cultural and humanitarian relations, Uzbekistan, Turkey, independence, education, culture, art, tourism, public diplomacy, civil society.*

Introduction

Cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey have deep historical roots and are characterized by intensive cooperation in various fields. After both countries gained independence in the early 1990s, these relations reached a new level, becoming one of the key factors in strengthening bilateral ties.

Cooperation in the fields of education, culture, art, tourism, and public diplomacy has played an important role in shaping mutual understanding and trust between the peoples of Uzbekistan and Turkey. Exchanges of students and teachers, joint cultural events, and participation in international exhibitions and festivals have contributed to cultural enrichment and the strengthening of interpersonal contacts.

In recent years, cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey have acquired special significance in the context of regional and global challenges. Both countries advocate for dialogue between religions and civilizations, and promote the ideas of tolerance and mutual respect.

An analysis of cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey allows us to identify the factors contributing to their development, assess their impact on bilateral relations, and determine the prospects for further cooperation. This is important for strengthening mutual understanding between the peoples of the two countries, as well as for promoting regional stability and international cooperation.

The purpose of the work

The aim of this article is to analyse the cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey during the years of independence, to identify the factors contributing to their development, and to assess their impact on bilateral relations.

Methods

Analysis of historical documents and literature on cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey.

Comparative analysis of cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey and other countries in the region.

Discussion of the results obtained

The analysis of cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey during the years of independence has shown that these relations have played a significant role in strengthening bilateral ties and promoting mutual understanding between the two countries. Cooperation in the fields of education, culture, art, tourism, and public diplomacy has contributed to the development of human capital, cultural enrichment, and the strengthening of people-to-people contacts.

Key findings of the analysis include:

1. Shared historical and cultural heritage: The common historical and cultural heritage of Uzbekistan and Turkey has provided a solid foundation for cooperation and has facilitated the establishment of close ties between the two peoples.

2. Political will: The political will of the leaders of both countries to develop and strengthen cultural and humanitarian relations has been reflected in the signing of numerous agreements and memorandums of understanding, as well as in the establishment of joint commissions and working groups.

3. Positive impact on civil society: Cultural and humanitarian relations have had a positive impact on the development of civil society in both countries. Cooperation in the fields of education and culture has contributed to the improving the level of education and cultural development of the population. The exchange of ideas and experiences has also helped to promote tolerance, mutual respect, and understanding.

4. Promotion of regional cooperation: Cultural and humanitarian relations have played an important role in promoting regional cooperation and stability. Uzbekistan and Turkey are both members of the Organization of Turkic States, and they have been actively involved in promoting cultural and humanitarian cooperation within the organization. This cooperation has helped to strengthen ties between the Turkic-speaking countries and has contributed to the promotion of regional peace and security.

One of the key factors contributing to the development of cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey has been the shared historical and cultural heritage of the two countries. This common heritage has provided a solid foundation for cooperation and has facilitated the establishment of close ties between the two peoples.

Another important factor has been the political will of the leaders of both countries to develop and strengthen cultural and humanitarian relations. This political will has been reflected in the signing of numerous agreements and memorandums of understanding, as well as in the establishment of joint commissions and working groups.

The analysis has also shown that cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey have had a positive impact on the development of civil society in both countries.

In addition, cultural and humanitarian relations have played an important role in promoting regional cooperation and stability. Uzbekistan and Turkey are both members of the Organization of Turkic States, and they have been actively involved in promoting cultural and humanitarian cooperation within the organization. This cooperation has helped to strengthen ties between the Turkic-speaking countries and has contributed to the promotion of regional peace and security.

Overall, the analysis has shown that cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey are an important and integral part of bilateral relations. These relations have played a significant role in strengthening ties between the two countries, promoting mutual understanding, developing civil society, and promoting regional cooperation. The continuation and

further development of these relations will contribute to the further strengthening of bilateral cooperation and the development of the two countries.

Conclusion

Cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey have played a significant role in strengthening bilateral ties and promoting mutual understanding between the two countries. Cooperation in the fields of education, culture, art, tourism, and public diplomacy has contributed to the development of human capital, cultural enrichment, and the strengthening of people-to-people contacts.

The analysis of these relations has shown that shared historical and cultural heritage, political will, and a commitment to regional cooperation have been key factors contributing to their development. Cultural and humanitarian relations have also had a positive impact on the development of civil society in both countries and have played an important role in promoting regional stability.

The continuation and further development of cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey will contribute to the further strengthening of bilateral cooperation and the development of the two countries. This will require continued political support, the implementation of joint projects and initiatives, and the promotion of people-to-people contacts.

By working together, Uzbekistan and Turkey can continue to build on their shared cultural and historical heritage to create a better future for their peoples and for the region as a whole.

In addition, the analysis has shown that cultural and humanitarian relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey have the potential to contribute to the following:

1. Strengthening regional cooperation: Uzbekistan and Turkey are both members of the Organization of Turkic States, and they can use their cultural and humanitarian cooperation to promote regional peace and security.

2. Promoting intercultural dialogue: The two countries can use their shared cultural heritage to promote intercultural dialogue and understanding between different cultures.

3. Addressing global challenges: Cultural and humanitarian cooperation can be used to address global challenges such as poverty, climate change, and terrorism.

By continuing to develop and strengthen their cultural and humanitarian relations, Uzbekistan and Turkey can make a positive contribution to the region and the world.

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